

Ice-shelf vibrations modeled by a full 3-D elastic model: field equations (version 8.1)

Y.V. Konovalov

ORCID: 0000-0002-8469-9706

*Department of Mathematics, MIREA - Russian Technological University, Vernadsky avenue 78,
Moscow, Russian Federation, 119454*

Correspondence to: Y.V. Konovalov (yu-v-k@yandex.ru)

Abstract

This version, like the previous version 7 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14878773>), considers the modeling of the oscillation of a system consisting of three components: (i) an ice shelf, (ii) seawater in a cavity under the ice shelf and (iii) meltwater lakes filling valleys on the ice shelf surface. The difference in the approximation of the momentum equations described the ice shelf deflections. This model based on the finite volume method of the momentum equations approximation, as considered in versions 5 and 6 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7697142>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252877>, <https://doi.org/10.1017/aog.2024.47>)

Both the sub-ice seawater flow and meltwater flow in lakes are treated as a “potential flow”. Accordingly, in this model, as in the previous version 7, both the subglacial flow of seawater and the flow of meltwater in lakes (long gravity waves on the surface of meltwater lakes) are described by the corresponding wave equations.

Numerical experiments were undertaken for an ice-shelf geometry, which corresponds to the geometry of Ward Hunt Ice Shelf, Ellesmere Island, Canadian Arctic (<https://doi.org/10.1017/jog.2022.3>, <https://doi.org/10.1017/jog.2023.58>).

As in the previous versions, the oscillations of the three-component system were modeled with harmonic incoming pressure perturbations and over a wide range of incoming wave frequencies. The wave equations and the corresponding boundary conditions imply the existence of eigen-frequencies, and the amplitude spectra obtained using the model reveal distinct resonant peaks, as were also observed in previous models.

1. Model description and field equations

This model is a generalization of the model described in versions 5 and 6 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7697142>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252877>, <https://doi.org/10.1017/aog.2024.47>). The model is based on a combination of different types of 2nd order partial differential equations: (i) momentum equations describing ice-shelf vibrations, (ii) wave equation describing sub-ice seawater flow in the cavity and (iii) wave equation describing long gravity waves on surface of meltwater lakes.

1.1 Basic equations

1.1.1 Momentum equations described the motion of an ice shelf

In this model, ice shelf deformations are described using the momentum equations written as the momentum balance equation in the volume V (bounded by the surface S) of an elastically deformable continuous medium, and have the following form (e.g. [1], [2], [3], [4]) (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7697142>)

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \int_V \rho U_i dV = \int_V \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_{ik}}{\partial x_k} + \rho g_i \right) dV \quad (1.1)$$

or

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \int_V \rho U_i dV = \int_S \sigma_{ik} dS_k + \int_V \rho g_i dV \quad (1.2)$$

where σ is the stress tensor; and ρ is the ice density; $i, k = 1,2,3$ or in terms of rectangular coordinate (XYZ) i, k means x, y, z ; U_i are displacements of an elastic continuous medium (displacements of ice) which are also denoted in rectangular coordinates as U, V, W : U, V and W are two horizontal and one vertical ice displacements, respectively.

As in previous versions/models (XYZ) is a rectangular coordinate system with the X -axis along the center line, and Z -axis pointing vertically up. The ice shelf has a length L along the center line. The geometry of the ice shelf is assumed to be given by lateral boundary functions $y_{1,2}(x)$ at sides labeled 1 and 2 and functions for the surface and base elevation, $h_{s,b}(x, y)$, denoted by subscripts s and b , respectively. Thus, the domain, which includes the volume of integration in equations (1), is $\Omega = \{0 < x < L, y_1(x) < y < y_2(x), h_b(x, y) < z < h_s(x, y)\}$.

1.1.2 Wave equation described sub-ice seawater flow in the cavity

Sub-ice water is assumed to be an incompressible inviscid fluid of uniform density. Another assumption is that water depth in the cavity below the ice shelf changes gradually in the horizontal directions. Thus, the ice-front and other such features are not considered here. Moreover, the ice is considered to be a continuous solid elastic plate. Under these three assumptions, sub-ice water flow is independent of z in a vertical column. Manipulating the governing equations of the shallow sub-ice water layer yields the wave equation (<https://doi.org/10.1038/274464a0>):

$$\frac{\partial^2 W_{sl}}{\partial t^2} = \frac{1}{\rho_w} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(d_0 \frac{\partial P'}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{1}{\rho_w} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(d_0 \frac{\partial P'}{\partial y} \right), \quad (2)$$

where ρ_w is sea water density; $d_0(x, y)$ is the depth of the sub-ice water layer; $W_{sl}(x, y, t)$ is the vertical deflection of the surface of sub-ice water layer and $W_{sl}(x, y, t) = W_b(x, y, t) = W(x, y, h_b(x, y), t)$ ($W_b(x, y, t)$ is the vertical deflection of the ice-shelf base) and $P'(x, y, t)$ is the deviation of the sub-ice water pressure from the hydrostatic value.

1.1.3 Wave equation described gravity waves on surfaces of the meltwater lakes

In this model, melt water in lakes is also considered as an incompressible inviscid fluid of uniform density. It is assumed that gravity waves in lakes are described by the wave equation for long gravity waves. The corresponding manipulation of the governing equations for the shallow meltwater layer in the lakes yields the wave equation (e.g. [2]):

$$\frac{\partial^2 \zeta}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2 W_s}{\partial t^2} = g \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(h_0 \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(h_0 \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial y} \right) \right), \quad (3)$$

where $\zeta(x, y, t)$ is the vertical deflection of the water surface in lakes (from the equilibrium surface level); $h_0(x, y)$ is the depth of the meltwater lakes; $W_s(x, y, t)$ is the vertical deflection of the ice-shelf surface, and $W_s(x, y, t) = W(x, y, h_s(x, y), t)$.

1.2 Boundary conditions

The boundary conditions for equations (1) are:

- (i) stress free ice surface and normal stress exerted by meltwater in regions on the ice surface where there are meltwater lakes;
- (ii) the normal stress exerted by seawater at the ice-shelf free edges and at the ice-shelf base; and
- (iii) rigidly fixed edges at the grounding line of the ice-shelf.

In this model, the boundary conditions are also (as in previous versions) considered as a linear combination

$$\alpha_1 F_i(U, V, W) + \alpha_2 \Phi_i(U, V, W) = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \quad (4)$$

where:

- (i) $F_i(U, V, W) = 0$ is the typical and well-known form of the boundary conditions where, for example, the condition on the ice-shelf surface is expressed as $\sigma_{ik} n_k = 0$ or $\sigma_{ik} n_k = -P_w n_i$ (\vec{n} is the unit vector normal to the surface, P_w is the meltwater pressure);
- (ii) $\Phi_i(U, V, W) = 0$ is the approximation based on the application of a *finite volume approach* to the approximation of the boundary conditions, taking in to account for the typical form of boundary conditions on the boundaries of an *elementary volume* (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252877>);
and
- (iii) the coefficients α_1 and α_2 satisfy the condition $\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 = 1$.

The boundary conditions for the subglacial seawater layer (for equation (2)) correspond to a frontal gravity incident ocean wave. They are

- (i) at $x = 0$: $\frac{\partial P'}{\partial x} = 0$;
- (ii) at $y = y_1, y = y_2$: $\frac{\partial P'}{\partial y} = 0$;
- (iii) at $x = L$: $P' = A_0 \rho_w g e^{i\omega t}$, where A_0 is the amplitude of the incident wave.

The boundary conditions for equation (3) correspond to the assumption that along the coastlines of the meltwater lakes the vertical deflection of the water surface $\zeta(x, y, t)$ is approximately equal to the vertical deflection of the ice-shelf surface $W_s(x, y, t)$, i.e. the boundary conditions are $\zeta(x, y, t) = W_s(x, y, t)$ along the coastlines.

1.3 Discretization of the model

Numerical solutions were obtained by a finite volume method, which is based on the standard coordinate transformation $x, y, z \rightarrow x, \eta = \frac{y-y_1}{y_2-y_1}, \xi = (h_s - z)/H$, where H is the ice thickness ($H = h_s - h_b$). The coordinate transformation maps the ice domain Ω into the rectangular parallelepiped $\Pi = \{0 \leq x \leq L; 0 \leq \eta \leq 1; 0 \leq \xi \leq 1\}$, which simplifies the numerical discretization.

A detailed description of the approximation of the momentum equations (1) was presented in version 5 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7697142>).

1.4 Equations for ice-shelf displacements

Constitutive relationships between stress tensor components and displacements correspond to Hooke's law (e.g., [3], [4]):

$$\sigma_{ij} = \frac{E}{1+\nu} \left(u_{ij} + \frac{\nu}{1-2\nu} u_{ll} \delta_{ij} \right), \quad (5)$$

where u_{ij} are the strain components, E - Young's modulus, ν - Poisson's ratio.

1.5 Ice-shelf harmonic vibrations. The eigenvalue problem.

(Essentially, this point repeats the assumptions made in previous versions [6-9]. All assumptions of this point that were valid for the previous models, are also valid for the model considered here)

It is assumed that for harmonic vibrations all variables are periodic in time, with the periodicity of the incident wave (of the forcing) given by the frequency ω , i.e.,

$$\tilde{\zeta}(x, y, z, t) = \zeta(x, y, z) e^{i\omega t}, \quad (6)$$

where $\tilde{\zeta} = \{U, V, W, \sigma_{ij}, \zeta\}$,

where we are interested in the real part of the variables expressed in complex form.

This assumption also implies that the full solution of the linear partial differential equations (1), (2), (3) is a sum of the solution for the steady-state flexure of the ice shelf and solution (6) for the time-dependent problem. In other words, solution (6) implies that the deformation due to the gravitational forcing can be separated from the vibration problem, i.e. the term ρg in the third equation from (1) as well as the appropriate terms in the boundary conditions (4) are absent from the final equations formulated for the vibration problem, because a time-independent solution accounting for them applies and is not of interest in this study.

The separation of variables in equation (6) and its substitution into equations (1), (2), (3) yields the same equations, but with the operator $\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2}$ replaced with the constant $-\omega^2$, i.e.

we obtain equation for $\zeta(x, y, z)$:

$$\mathcal{L} \zeta = -\omega^2 \zeta, \quad (7)$$

where \mathcal{L} is a linear partial differential operator.

The numerical solution of equation (7) at different values of ω yields the dependence of ζ on the frequency of the forcing ω . When the frequency of the forcing converges to the eigenfrequency of the system, we observe the typical rapid increase of deformation/stresses in the spectra in the form of the resonant peaks.

Note that here, the term ‘‘eigenvalue’’ refers to the eigenfrequency (ω_n) of the ice/water system or corresponding periodicity ($T_n = \frac{2\pi}{\omega_n}$). As mentioned previously, the term ‘‘eigenvalue’’ is employed in the same meaning like in a Sturm-Liouville Eigenvalue Problem (e.g. [10]). Eigenvalues (where resonant peaks would be observed) are denoted by the letters ω_n or T_n with the subscript n (or other), which is integer, because the array of the eigenvalues is a countable set.

Letters ω or T without the subscript denote the non-resonant values of frequency or periodicity of the ice/water system. They are defined by the frequency of the incident wave (of the forcing).

The eigenvalues can be derived from the equation $D(\omega) = 0$, where D is the determinant of the matrix, which results from the discretization of equation (7) and of the corresponding boundary conditions. However, the probability of the appearance of the forcing at any specific frequency is practically zero. This can be seen when we consider only events within the frequency range $(\omega_i - \Delta\omega, \omega_i + \Delta\omega)$. The probability of a forcing that is within the frequency range, is non-zero:

$$p\{\omega \in (\omega_i - \Delta\omega, \omega_i + \Delta\omega)\} = \frac{2\Delta\omega}{\Omega}, \quad (8)$$

where Ω is the width of the range in omega space, which includes all possible frequencies of the forcing. Equation (8) also assumes that the events have equal probabilities in different parts of Ω .

Thus, the probability of the resonant-like motion is higher when the value $\Delta\omega$, which is defined by the width of the resonant peak, is higher too. Therefore, the width of the resonant peaks is an important parameter, from a practical standpoint, because it defines the probability of the suitable resonant-like motion.

Computation of the spectra, such as provided below, thus provides important information about the width of resonant peaks within the likely range of forcing frequencies found in nature. By assessing the widths of such peaks, a better understanding of the probability that any one specific forcing event, at a specific ω can be assessed.

2. Code input parameters and code output results

The numerical experiments with forced vibrations were undertaken for a physically idealized ice shelf with the geometry shown in Figure 1. In the undeformed ice shelf, the four edges had coordinates $x = 0, x = L, y_1 = 0, y_2 = B$, where L is the plate length along the x -axis and B is the plate width along the y -axis ($B = y_2 - y_1$, see equations (1)).

The ice plate had only one fixed edge (at $x = 0$), while the other edges (at $x = L, y_1 = 0, y_2 = B$) were free. This is the special case of an ice shelf, which is also known as an “ice tongue” (<https://doi.org/10.1038/274464a0>). The intact ice tongue was 2 km in longitudinal extent, 0.1-0.2 km width.

The “rolling” surface morphology (<https://doi.org/10.1017/jog.2022.3>, <https://doi.org/10.1017/jog.2023.58>) was modeled by sinusoidally varying ice thickness

$$H(x) = H_0 + A_H \frac{\rho_w}{\rho} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi x}{\Delta l_r}\right), \quad (9)$$

where A_H is the amplitude of ice thickness oscillations, which was considered as a parameter of the models; Δl_r is the spatial periodicity of the “rolls” (Δl_r in the models was equal to 0.5 km); H_0 in the models was equal to 25m. Essentially, this ice tongue was considered as a part of the Ward Hunt Ice Shelf.

The parameters of the ice shelf with rolling surface morphology are listed in the [lines 29-31](#) of the program code. They are

- a) the spatial periodicity of the rolls Δl_r (designated as T_Cr in the code)
- b) the amplitude of ice thickness oscillations depth A_{cr} (designated as $Depth_Cr$ in the code);

In accordance with equation (9), [lines 140-149](#) of the code define the “rolling” surface morphology (sinusoidally varying ice thickness).

Figure 2 shows how the depth of meltwater lakes changes along the centerline of the ice shelf with the rolling surface morphology. The steady (undisturbed) level/height of the surface of meltwater lakes is determined by the parameter L_{Lakes} in **line 34** of the code. According to the value of the L_{Lakes} parameter, the depth of meltwater lakes is determined (h_0 in equation (3)) in **lines 191-218** of the code.

In this model, the area of definition of the function $\zeta(x, y, t)$ (equation (3)) is expanded to the entire region where the ice is located: $0 < x < L; y_1(x) < y < y_2(x)$. This means that the function $\zeta(x, y, t)$ is vertical deflection of the water surface in lakes where there are meltwater lakes (where $h_s(x, y) < L_{Lakes}$), and $\zeta(x, y, t)$ is vertical displacement of the ice shelf surface, i.e. $\zeta(x, y, t) = W_s(x, y, t)$ for $h_s(x, y) > L_{Lakes}$. The function $\zeta(x, y, t)$ is defined in **lines 699-951** of the code.

As in the previous version 7, the main cycle (**lines 656-38388**) where the frequency of the incident wave (forcing) is varied, includes (i) the code where the solution of equation (3) is obtained (**lines 787-842**); (ii) the code that provides the solution to the momentum equations (1) (**lines 956-38133**) and (iii) the code that provides the solution to the equation (2) (**lines 38154-38306**). Accordingly, having determined the maximum value of the vertical displacement of the ice shelf (**lines 38373-38379**) (or maximum value of free energy) for different values of the frequency of the forcing we obtain the amplitude spectrum (or energy spectrum).

Figures 3-92 show a) the function $\zeta(x, y, \omega)$, i.e. the vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes, - in the corresponding mode obtained for a given periodicity/frequency; b) ice shelf base vertical deflection; c) the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$, where $W_s(x, y, \omega)$ is the vertical deflection of the ice shelf surface.

Figures 3-17 show a series of results obtained for the amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 8\text{ m}$ and for $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0$ (**pages 15-29**).

Figures 18-32 show a series of results obtained for the amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 8\text{ m}$ and for $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0$ (**pages 30-44**).

Figures 33-47 show a series of results obtained for the amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 10\text{ m}$ and for $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0$ (**pages 45-59**).

Figures 48-62 show a series of results obtained for the amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 10\text{ m}$ and for $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0$ (**pages 60-74**).

Figures 63-77 show a series of results obtained for the amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 12\text{ m}$ and for $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0$ (**pages 75-89**).

Figures 78-92 show a series of results obtained for the amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 12\text{ m}$ and for $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0$ (**pages 90-104**).

The output results of the code are the amplitude spectra (the amplitude of the ice shelf deflection versus periodicity/frequency of the forcing): **lines 38396-38460**

In particular, **Figure 93** show the amplitude spectra obtained in the experiments, when (i) meltwater lakes were present and (ii) there were no meltwater lakes on ice shelf surface (as in previous versions 5, 6 of the model) (**pages 105-106**).

Figure 1. The ice-shelf and the cavity profiles considered in the numerical experiments. **1** – ice shelf surface; **2** – ice shelf base; **3** – sea bottom. The amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 18 \text{ m}$. Spatial periodicity (Δl_r) of the “rolls” is equal to 0.5 km .

Fig. 2a

Fig. 2b

Fig. 2c

Figure 2. The profiles of (1) ice shelf surface elevation and (2) meltwater lakes depth along the centerline: **(a)** - $A_H = 8\text{ m}$; **(b)** - $A_H = 12\text{ m}$; **(c)** $A_H = 18\text{ m}$.

Amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 8 \text{ m}$ (see Figure 1).

$$\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0.$$

Fig. 3a

Fig. 3b

Fig. 3c

Figure 3. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 10\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 8 \text{ m}$.

Fig. 4a

Fig. 4b

Fig. 4c

Figure 4. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 15\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 8\text{ m}$.

Fig. 5a

Fig. 5b

Fig. 5c

Figure 5. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 20\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 8\text{ m}$.

Fig. 6a

Fig. 6b

Fig. 6c

Figure 6. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 25s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 8 m$.

Fig. 7a

Fig. 7b

Fig. 7c

Figure 7. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 30s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 8 m$.

Fig. 8a

Fig. 8b

Fig. 8c

Figure 8. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 40s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 8 m$.

Fig. 9a

Fig. 9b

Fig. 9c

Figure 9. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 50s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 8 m$.

Fig. 10a

Fig. 10b

Fig. 10c

Figure 10. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 60\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 8\text{ m}$.

Fig. 11a

Fig. 11b

Fig. 11c

Figure 11. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 70s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 8 m$.

Fig. 12a

Fig. 12b

Fig. 12c

Figure 12. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 80s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 8 m$.

Fig. 13a

Fig. 13b

Fig. 13c

Figure 13. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 90s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 8 m$.

Fig. 14a

Fig. 14b

Fig. 14c

Figure 14. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 110s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 8 m$.

Fig. 15a

Fig. 15b

Fig. 15c

Figure 15. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 130s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 8 m$.

Fig. 16a

Fig. 16b

Fig. 16c

Figure 16. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 150s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 8 m$.

Fig. 17a

Fig. 17b

Fig. 17c

Figure 17. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 170s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 8 m$.

Amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 8 \text{ m}$ (see Figure 1).

$$\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0.$$

Fig. 18a

Fig. 18b

Fig. 18c

Figure 18. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 10\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 8 \text{ m}$.

Fig. 19a

Fig. 19b

Fig. 19c

Figure 19. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 15\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 8\text{ m}$.

Fig. 20a

Fig. 20b

Fig. 20c

Figure 20. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 20\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 8\text{ m}$.

Fig. 21a

Fig. 21b

Fig. 21c

Figure 21. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 25\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 8\text{ m}$.

Fig. 22a

Fig. 22b

Fig. 22c

Figure 22. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 30s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 8 m$.

Fig. 23a

Fig. 23b

Fig. 23c

Figure 23. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 40\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 8\text{ m}$.

Fig. 24a

Fig. 24b

Fig. 24c

Figure 24. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 50\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 8\text{ m}$.

Fig. 25a

Fig. 25b

Fig. 25c

Figure 25. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 60\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 8\text{ m}$.

Fig. 26a

Fig. 26b

Fig. 26c

Figure 26. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 70s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 8 m$.

Fig. 27a

Fig. 27b

Fig. 27c

Figure 27. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 80s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 8 m$.

Fig. 28a

Fig. 28b

Fig. 28c

Figure 28. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 90\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 8\text{ m}$.

Fig. 29a

Fig. 29b

Fig. 29c

Figure 29. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 110s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 8 m$.

Fig. 30a

Fig. 30b

Fig. 30c

Figure 30. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 130s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 8 m$.

Fig. 31a

Fig. 31b

Fig. 31c

Figure 31. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 150s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 8 m$.

Fig. 32a

Fig. 32b

Fig. 32c

Figure 32. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 170s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 8 m$.

Amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 10 \text{ m}$ (see Figure 1).

$$\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0$$

Fig. 33a

Fig. 33b

Fig. 33c

Figure 33. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 10 \text{ s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 10 \text{ m}$.

Fig. 34a

Fig. 34b

Fig. 34c

Figure 34. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 15\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 10\text{ m}$.

Fig. 35a

Fig. 35b

Fig. 35c

Figure 35. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 20s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 10 m$.

Fig. 36a

Fig. 36b

Fig. 36c

Figure 36. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 25\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 10\text{ m}$.

Fig. 37a

Fig. 37b

Fig. 37c

Figure 37. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 30s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 10 m$.

Fig. 38a

Fig. 38b

Fig. 38c

Figure 38. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 40s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 10 m$.

Fig. 39a

Fig. 39b

Fig. 39c

Figure 39. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 50\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 10\text{ m}$.

Fig. 40a

Fig. 40b

Fig. 40c

Figure 40. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 60\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 10\text{ m}$.

Fig. 41a

Fig. 41b

Fig. 41c

Figure 41. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 70\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 10\text{ m}$.

Fig. 42a

Fig. 42b

Fig. 42c

Figure 42. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 80s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 10 m$.

Fig. 43a

Fig. 43b

Fig. 43c

Figure 43. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 90\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 10\text{ m}$.

Fig. 44a

Fig. 44b

Fig. 44c

Figure 44. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 110s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 10 m$.

Fig. 45a

Fig. 45b

Fig. 45c

Figure 45. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 130\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 10\text{ m}$.

Fig. 46a

Fig. 46b

Fig. 46c

Figure 46. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 150s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 10 m$.

Fig. 47a

Fig. 47b

Fig. 47c

Figure 47. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 170s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 10 m$.

Amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 10\text{ m}$ (see Figure 1).

$$\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0$$

Fig. 48a

Fig. 48b

Fig. 48c

Figure 48. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 10\text{ s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 10\text{ m}$.

Fig. 49a

Fig. 49b

Fig. 49c

Figure 49. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_\zeta(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 15\text{ s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 10\text{ m}$.

Fig. 50a

Fig. 50b

Fig. 50c

Figure 50. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 20\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 10\text{ m}$.

Fig. 51a

Fig. 51b

Fig. 51c

Figure 51. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 25\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 10\text{ m}$.

Fig. 52a

Fig. 52b

Fig. 52c

Figure 52. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 30\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 10\text{ m}$.

Fig. 53a

Fig. 53b

Fig. 53c

Figure 53. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_{\zeta}(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 40\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 10\text{ m}$.

Fig. 54a

Fig. 54b

Fig. 54c

Figure 54. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 50s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 10 m$.

Fig. 55a

Fig. 55b

Fig. 55c

Figure 55. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 60s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 10 m$.

Fig. 56a

Fig. 56b

Fig. 56c

Figure 56. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 70\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 10\text{ m}$.

Fig. 57a

Fig. 57b

Fig. 57c

Figure 57. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 80s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 10 m$.

Fig. 58a

Fig. 58b

Fig. 58c

Figure 58. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 90\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 10\text{ m}$.

Fig. 59a

Fig. 59b

Fig. 59c

Figure 59. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 110\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 10\text{ m}$.

Fig. 60a

Fig. 60b

Fig. 60c

Figure 60. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 130s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 10 m$.

Fig. 61a

Fig. 61b

Fig. 61c

Figure 61. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 150s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 10 m$.

Fig. 62a

Fig. 62b

Fig. 62c

Figure 62. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 170\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 10\text{ m}$.

Amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 12 \text{ m}$ (see Figure 1).

$$\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0$$

Fig. 63a

Fig. 63b

Fig. 63c

Figure 63. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 10\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 12 \text{ m}$.

Fig. 64a

Fig. 64b

Fig. 64c

Figure 64. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 15\text{ s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 65a

Fig. 65b

Fig. 65c

Figure 65. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 20\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 66a

Fig. 66b

Fig. 66c

Figure 66. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_{\zeta}(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 25\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 67a

Fig. 67b

Fig. 67c

Figure 67. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 30\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 68a

Fig. 68b

Fig. 68c

Figure 68. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 40\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 69a

Fig. 69b

Fig. 69c

Figure 69. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 50s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 70a

Fig. 70b

Fig. 70c

Figure 70. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 60s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 71a

Fig. 71b

Fig. 71c

Figure 71. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 70\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 72a

Fig. 72b

Fig. 72c

Figure 72. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 80s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 73a

Fig. 73b

Fig. 73c

Figure 73. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 90\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 74a

Fig. 74b

Fig. 74c

Figure 74. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 110s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 75a

Fig. 75b

Fig. 75c

Figure 75. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 130s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 76a

Fig. 76b

Fig. 76c

Figure 76. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 150s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 77a

Fig. 77b

Fig. 77c

Figure 77. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 170s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 12 \text{ m}$ (see Figure 1).

$$\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0$$

Fig. 78a

Fig. 78b

Fig. 78c

Figure 78. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 10 \text{ s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 12 \text{ m}$.

Fig. 79a

Fig. 79b

Fig. 79c

Figure 79. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 15\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 80a

Fig. 80b

Fig. 80c

Figure 80. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 20s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 81a

Fig. 81b

Fig. 81c

Figure 81. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 25s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 82a

Fig. 82b

Fig. 82c

Figure 82. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 30s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 83a

Fig. 83b

Fig. 83c

Figure 83. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 40\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 84a

Fig. 84b

Fig. 84c

Figure 84. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 50\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 85a

Fig. 85b

Fig. 85c

Figure 85. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 60\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 86a

Fig. 86b

Fig. 86c

Figure 86. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 70\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 87a

Fig. 87b

Fig. 87c

Figure 87. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 80s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 88a

Fig. 88b

Fig. 88c

Figure 88. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_{\zeta}(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 90\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 89a

Fig. 89b

Fig. 89c

Figure 89. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 110s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 90a

Fig. 90b

Fig. 90c

Figure 90. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 130s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 91a

Fig. 91b

Fig. 91c

Figure 91. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 150s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 92a

Fig. 92b

Fig. 92c

Figure 92. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 170s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 93a

Fig. 93b

Fig. 93c

Fig. 93d

Fig. 93f

Figure 93. The amplitude spectra obtained in the experiments, when (i) there were the meltwater lakes and (ii) there were no meltwater lakes on ice shelf surface (version 6 of the model). **a)** $A_H = 8m$; **b)** $A_H = 10m$; **c)** $A_H = 12m$; **d)** $A_H = 14m$; **f)** $A_H = 16m$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$.

References

1. Lamb, H.: Hydrodynamics. (6th ed.). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1994.
2. Landau, L.D., Lifshitz, E.M.: Fluid Mechanics (Vol. 6). Pergamon Press., New York, USA, 1987
3. Landau, L.D., E.M. Lifshitz: Theory of Elasticity. (3rd ed.). Oxford: Butterworth-Heinemann, (Vol. 7), 1986.
4. Lurie, A.I.: Theory of Elasticity. Berlin: Springer, (Foundations of Engineering Mechanics), 2005.
5. Holdsworth, G. & J. Glynn: Iceberg calving from floating glaciers by a vibrating mechanism. *Nature*, 274, 464-466, 1978. <https://doi.org/10.1038/274464a0>
6. Konovalov Y.V. (2019) Ice-shelf vibrations modeled by a full 3-D elastic model. *Annals of Glaciology*, 60(79), 68-74. doi:10.1017/aog.2019.9 (<http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/aog.2019.9>)
7. Konovalov, Y.V. Abatement of Ocean-Wave Impact by Crevasses in an Ice Shelf. *J. Mar. Sci. Eng.*, 9(1), 46, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse9010046>
8. Konovalov Y.V. Modeling of Ocean Wave Impacts on Crevassed Ice Shelves. *Seismological Research Letters* 2023; 94 (3): 1526–1535. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1785/0220220263>
9. Konovalov Y.V. (2025) Bragg scattering of surface-gravity waves by an ice shelf with rolling surface morphology. *Annals of Glaciology* 66, e6, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1017/aog.2024.47>
10. Tikhonov, A.N., Samarskii, A.A.: Equations of Mathematical Physics. Pergamon Press Ltd., USA, 1963

11. Coffey NB, MacAyeal DR, Copland L and others (2022) Enigmatic surface rolls of the Ellesmere Ice Shelf. *Journal of Glaciology*, **68**(271), 867-878 (doi:10.1017/jog.2022.3)
12. Nekrasov P, MacAyeal DR (2023) Ocean wave blocking by periodic surface rolls fortifies Arctic ice shelves. *J. Glaciol.*, 1-11 (doi:10.1017/jog.2023.58)
13. Ashcroft, N.W., & Mermin, N.D.: Solid state physics. Books Cole, Belmont, CA, 1976
14. Balmforth, N.J., & Craster, R.V.: Ocean waves and ice sheets. *J. Fluid Mech.*, 395, 89-124, doi: 10.1017/S0022112099005145, 1999
15. Bassis, J.N., Fricker, H.A., Coleman, R., Minster, J.-B.: An investigation into the forces that drive ice-shelf rift propagation on the Amery Ice Shelf, East Antarctica. *J. Glaciol.*, 54 (184), 17-27, doi: 10.3189/002214308784409116, 2008
16. Bennetts, L.G., Biggs, N.R.T., Porter, D.: The interaction of flexural-gravity waves with periodic geometries. *Wave Motion*, 46 (1), 57-73, doi.org/10.1016/j.wavemoti.2008.08.002, 2009
17. Bennets, L., Squire, V.: Wave scattering by multiple rows of circular ice floes. *J. Fluid Mech.*, 639, 213-238. doi:10.1017/S0022112009991017, 2009
18. Bennets, L., Williams, T.: Wave scattering by ice floes and polynyas of arbitrary shape. *J Fluid Mech.*, 662, 5-35. doi:10.1017/S0022112010004039, 2010
19. Bennetts, L.G., Squire V.A.: On the calculation of an attenuation coefficient for transects of ice-covered ocean. *Proc. R. Soc. A.*, 468, 136-162, doi:10.1098/rspa.2011.0155, 2012
20. Bennetts LG, Williams TD, Porter R (2024) A thin-plate approximation for ocean wave interactions with an ice shelf. *J. Fluid Mech.*, **984**(A48) (doi:10.1017/jfm.2024.200)

21. Bromirski, P.D., Sergienko, O.V., MacAyeal, D.R.: Transoceanic infragravity waves impacting Antarctic ice shelves. *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 37, L02502. doi:10.1029/2009GL041488, 2009
22. Bromirski, P., Stephen, R.: Response of the Ross Ice Shelf, Antarctica, to ocean gravity-wave forcing. *Ann. Glaciol.*, 53(60), 163-172. doi:10.3189/2012AoG60A058, 2012
23. Bromirski, P. D., Diez, A., Gerstoft, P., Stephen, R. A., Bolmer, T., Wiens, D. A., Aster, R. C., and Nyblade, A.: Ross ice shelf vibrations. *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 42, 7589–7597, doi:10.1002/2015GL065284, 2015
24. Gerstoft P., Bromirski P., Chen Z., Stephen R.A, Aster R.C., Wiens D.A., Nyblade, A.: Tsunami excitation of the Ross Ice Shelf, Antarctica. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 141(5), 3526, doi:10.1121/1.4987434, 2017
25. Chen, Z., Bromirski, P., Gerstoft, P., Stephen, R., Wiens, D., Aster, R., & Nyblade, A.: Ocean-excited plate waves in the Ross and Pine Island Glacier ice shelves. *J. Glaciol.*, 64(247), 730-744, doi:10.1017/jog.2018.66, 2018
26. Chen, Z., Bromirski, P., D, Gerstoft, P., Stephen, R. A., Lee, W. S., Yun, S., Olinger, S.D., Aster R.C., Wiens D.A., Nyblade A.A.: Ross Ice Shelf icequakes associated with ocean gravity wave activity. *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 46, 8893– 8902, doi:10.1029/2019GL084123, 2019
27. Chou, T.: Band structure of surface flexural-gravity waves along periodic interfaces. *J. Fluid Mech.*, 369, 333-350, 1998.
28. Freed-Brown, J., Amundson J., MacAyeal, D., & Zhang, W.: Blocking a wave: Frequency band gaps in ice shelves with periodic crevasses. *Ann. Glaciol.*, 53(60), 85-89, doi: 10.3189/2012AoG60A120, 2012
29. Gerstoft, P., Bromirski, P., Chen, Z., Stephen, R.A, Aster, R.C., Wiens, D.A., Nyblade, A.: Tsunami excitation of the Ross Ice Shelf, Antarctica. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 141(5), 3526, doi:10.1121/1.4987434, 2017

30. Godin, O. A, Zabotin, N. A.: Resonance vibrations of the Ross Ice Shelf and observations of persistent atmospheric waves. *J. Geophys. Res. Space Phys.*, **121**, 10157-10171, doi:10.1002/2016JA023226, 2016
31. Goodman, D.J., Wadhams, P., & Squire, V.A.: The flexural response of a tabular ice island to ocean swell. *Ann. Glaciol.*, **1**, 23–27, 1980
32. Hattersley-Smith G, Crary AP and Christie RL (1955) Northern Ellesmere Island, 1953 and 1954. *Arctic*, **8**(1), 3–36
33. Hattersley-Smith G (1957) The rolls on the Ellesmere Ice Shelf. *Arctic*, **10**(1), 32–44
34. Holdsworth, G.: Tidal interaction with ice shelves. *Ann. Geophys.*, **33**, 133-146, 1977
35. Hughes, T. J.: West Antarctic ice streams. *Reviews of Geophysics and Space Physics*, **15**(1), 1-46, 1977
36. Ilyas, M., Meylan, M.H., Lamichhane, B., Bennetts, L.G.: Time-domain and modal response of ice shelves to wave forcing using the finite element method. *J. Fluids and Structures*, **80**, 113-131, doi:10.1016/j.jfluidstructs.2018.03.010, 2018
37. Kalyanaraman B., Bennetts L.G., Lamichhane B., Meylan M.H.: On the shallow-water limit for modelling ocean-wave induced ice-shelf vibrations. *Wave Motion*, **90**, 1-16, doi: 10.1016/j.wavemoti.2019.04.004, 2019
38. Kalyanaraman B., Meylan M.H., Bennetts L.G., Lamichhane B.P.: A coupled fluid-elasticity model for the wave forcing of an ice-shelf. *J. Fluids and Structures*, **97**, 103074, doi: 10.1016/j.jfluidstructs.2020.103074, 2020
39. Lingle, C. S., Hughes, T. J., Kollmeyer, R. C.: Tidal flexure of Jakobshavn Glacier, West Greenland. *J. Geophys. Res.*, **86**(B5), 3960-3968, 1981
40. MacAyeal, D.R., Okal, E.A., Aster, R.C., Bassis, J.N., Brunt, K.M., Cathles, L.M., Drucker, R., Fricker, H.A., Kim, Y.-J., Martin, S., Okal, M.H., Sergienko, O.V., Sponsler, M.P., & Thom, J.E.: Transoceanic wave propagation links iceberg calving

- margins of Antarctica with storms in tropics and Northern Hemisphere. *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 33, L17502. doi:10.1029/2006GL027235, 2006
41. MacAyeal, D., Sergienko, O., Banwell, A.: A model of viscoelastic ice-shelf flexure. *J. Glaciol.*, 61(228), 635-645, doi:10.3189/2015JoG14J169, 2015
42. McNeil, S., M.H. Meylan, Time-Dependent Modelling of the Wave-Induced Vibration of Ice Shelves. *J. Mar. Sci. Eng.*, 11, 1191, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse11061191>,
43. Massom, R.A.; Scambos, T.A.; Bennetts, L.G.; Reid, P.; Squire, V.A.; Stammerjohn, S.E. Antarctic ice shelf disintegration triggered by sea ice loss and ocean swell. *Nature*, 558, 383–389, 2018
44. Mei, C.C.: Resonant reflection of surface water waves by periodic sandbars. *J. Fluid Mech.*, 152, 315-335, doi: S0022112085000714, 1985
45. Meylan, M., Squire, V.A., & Fox, C.: Towards realism in modelling ocean wave behavior in marginal ice zones. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 102(C10), 22981–22991, 1997
46. Meylan, M., Bennetts, L., Hosking, R., Catt, E. On the calculation of normal modes of a coupled ice-shelf/sub-ice-shelf cavity system. *J. Glaciol.*, 63(240), 751-754. doi:10.1017/jog.2017.27, 2017
47. Nekrasov, P. & D. MacAyeal. Ocean wave blocking by periodic surface rolls fortifies Arctic ice shelves. *J. Glaciol.*, 1-11. doi:10.1017/jog.2023.58, 2023
48. Papathanasiou, T. K., Karperaki, A. E., Theotokoglou, E. E., and Belibassakis, K. A.: Hydroelastic analysis of ice shelves under long wave excitation, *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci.*, 15, 1851–1857, doi:10.5194/nhess-15-1851-2015, 2015
49. Papathanasiou T.K., Karperaki, A.E., Belibassakis K.A.: On the resonant hydroelastic behaviour of ice shelves, *Ocean Modelling*, 133, 11-26, doi:10.1016/j.ocemod.2018.10.008, 2019
50. Reeh, N., Christensen, E.L., Mayer, C., Olesen, O.B.: Tidal bending of glaciers: a linear viscoelastic approach. *Ann. Glaciol.*, 37, 83–89, 2003

51. Robin, G. de Q.: Seismic shooting and related investigations. In Norwegian-British-Swedish Antarctic Expedition, Sci. Results 5, Glaciology 3, Norsk Polarinstitut (pp. 1949-1952). Oslo: University Press, 1958
52. Rosier, S.H.R., Gudmundsson, G.H., & Green, J.A.M.: Insights into ice stream dynamics through modeling their response to tidal forcing. *The Cryosphere*, 8, 1763–1775, 2014
53. Scambos, T.A., Hulbe, C., Fahnestock, M., Bohlander, J.: The link between climate warming and break-up of ice shelves in the Antarctic Peninsula. *J. Glaciol.*, 46(154), 516-530, doi:10.3189/172756500781833043, 2000
54. Shearman, E.D.R.: Radio science and oceanography, *Radio Sci.*, 18(3), 299–320, doi:10.1029/RS018i003p00299, 1983
55. Sheng, P.: Introduction to wave scattering, localization and mesoscopic phenomena. Springer, Berlin, 2006
56. Schmeltz, M., Rignot, E., & MacAyeal, D.R.: Tidal flexure along ice-sheets margins: Comparison of InSAR with an elastic plate model. *Ann. Glaciol.*, 34, 202-208, 2001
57. Schulson, E.M.: The Structure and Mechanical Behavior of Ice. *JOM*, 51 (2), 21-27, 1999
58. Sergienko, O.V.: Elastic response of floating glacier ice to impact of long-period ocean waves. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 115, F04028. doi:10.1029/2010JF001721, 2010
59. Sergienko, O. Normal modes of a coupled ice-shelf/sub-ice-shelf cavity system. *J. Glaciol.*, 59, 76–80, 2013
60. Sergienko, O.V. Behavior of flexural gravity waves on ice shelves: Application to the Ross Ice Shelf. *J. Geophys. Res. Oceans*, 122, 6147–6164, 2017
61. Smith, A.M.: The use of tiltmeters to study the dynamics of Antarctic ice shelf grounding lines. *J. Glaciol.*, 37, 51–58, 1991
62. Squire, V.A., Dugan, J.P., Wadhams, P., Rottier, P.J., & Liu, A.K.: Of ocean waves and sea ice. *Annu. Rev. Fluid Mech.*, 27, 115–168, 1995

63. Stephenson, S.N.: Glacier flexure and the position of grounding lines: measurements by tiltmeter on Rutford Ice Stream, Antarctica. *Ann. Glaciol.*, 5, 165-169, 1984
64. Turcotte, D.L., Schubert, G.: *Geodynamics*. (3rd ed.). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2002
65. Van der Veen C.J.: Fracture mechanics approach to penetration of bottom crevasses on glaciers. *Cold Reg. Sci. Technol.*, 27(3), 213-223, 1998
66. Vaughan, D.G.: Tidal flexure at ice shelf margins. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 100(B4), 6213–6224, doi:10.1029/94JBO2467, 1995
67. Wadhams, P.: The seasonal ice zone. In Untersteiner, N. (Ed.), *Geophysics of sea ice* (pp. 825–991), London: Plenum Press, 1986
68. Walker, R.T., Parizek, B.R., Alley, R.B., Anandakrishnan, S., Riverman, K.L., Christianson, K.: Ice-shelf tidal flexure and subglacial pressure variations. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 361, 422–428, doi: 10.1016/j.epsl.2012.11.008, 2013